

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

IDENTIFICATION, ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS OF SUSPECTED ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL AT SSIMS & RC, DAVANGERE

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 12/12/2017

Available online

01/01/2018

Keywords

Adverse Drug Reaction,
Adr Monitoring Centre,
Pharmacovigilance,
Causality Assessment.

ABSTRACT

Adverse drug reactions constitute for about 5% of all hospital admissions in India. And it has become one of the leading causes of mortality and morbidity. Due to the use of newer drugs and different prescribing habits the patterns of ADRs may vary in different hospitals. The objective of the study was to identify, assess and analyze the causative drugs associated with various adverse drug reactions and to report clinical patterns of adverse drug reactions in patients to Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring Centre at SSIMS & RC, Davangere. The prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months. A strict confidentiality was maintained about the patients details. The data was collected from the identified patient's case sheets. The prescriptions given to the patient was noted on the data collection form. Of the total of 61 reactions reported the most commonly implicated organ system were skin (63.93%). There were 30 males and 31 females. The major causative drug class was antimicrobials (42.62%). More than half of the reactions were classified as probable (67.21%) according to Naranjo's scale. In this study a total of 30 (49.18%) patients were recovered and 22 (36.07%) patients were recovering during the time of last assessment. In majority of the ADRs reported, the offending drugs were withdrawn (68.85%) and symptomatic treatment was given (70.49%). In our study most of the ADRs were definitely preventable (59.02%). Our study was conducted to improve public health and patient safety by increasing the risk awareness among health care professionals.

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Please cite this article in press as **Miss. Anu Theresa et al.** Identification, Assessment and Analysis of Suspected Adverse Drug Reactions in A Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital at SSIMS & RC, Davangere. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2017;7(12).

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INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (2000) defines Adverse Drug Reactions (ADRs) as a reaction which is noxious and unintended and which occurs at doses normally used in humans for prevention, diagnosis or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological functions.[1]

Pharmacovigilance is “The Pharmacological science relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects, particularly long term and short term side effects of medicines.” [2] As per 2012, there are over 7 million adverse reaction reports in the WHO individual case safety reports (ICSR) data base. Medicinal Product Records in WHO-Drug dictionary, March 1, 2006, for the Top 15 Countries shows that in spite of India having 40,800 Medicinal Product with 14,500 Product Names and 2,100 Combination of Ingredients, compared to United States with 72,700 Medicinal Product, 9,100 Product Names and 3,800 Combination of Ingredients, India is way behind them in reporting ADRs. In such a scenario, the Pharmacovigilance program initiated by Central Drugs Standard control Organization (CDSCO) of Indian government promises to maintain a close watch over the use of drugs and their effects on people. NCC-PvPI monitors the ADRs among Indian population and helps the regulatory authority of India (CDSCO) in taking decision for safe use of medicines.[3]

In many countries (including India) a Pharmacovigilance system is operational; however, under-reporting is a major problem. An increase has been observed in the current reporting culture of ADRs under Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PvPI) after conducting regular training and awareness programme and circulating the ‘PvPI Drug Safety Newsletter’. The data were entered manually into VigiFlow along with the mandatory field of ‘Information on Primary Source’ where a reporter has to specify his/her name, contact details and qualification.[4]

Incidence of ADRs in Indian population ranges between 1.8% and 25.1% with 8% resulting in hospitalization.[5] Elderly and hospitalized patients are reported to be more susceptible to ADRs than the adult population (16.6% vs. 4.1%).[6]

Important risk factors for ADRs are multiple medications, elderly age group, new drugs, alcohol intake, conditions of reduced hepatic / renal functions, pregnancy and breast feeding.[7] Polypharmacy is known to increase the risk of adverse drug reaction (ADRs), drug-drug and drug-disease interaction.[8]

The purpose of the study was to identify, assess and analyze the causative drugs associated with various adverse drug reactions and to report clinical patterns of adverse drug reactions in patients to Adverse Drug Reaction Monitoring Centre at SSIMS & RC, Davangere. It is in everyone’s interest to minimize the chances of ADR occurrence and to this end, government regulatory bodies and pharmacology industry collaborate to ensure adequate screening of new products. Present study was undertaken to create awareness and manifest the necessity and importance in reporting ADRs.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

- Informed Consent Form
- Patient Data Collection Form
- CDSCO Form

Study Design:

The present study is prospective observational study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The ethical clearance for the study was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Bapuji Pharmacy College, Davangere.

Selection Procedures

The patients were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

All patients of either gender having information of ADRs in the case sheets (both inpatients and outpatients) coming to SSIMS & RC Hospital, Davangere.

Exclusion criteria:

All patients involved in over-dosage, abuse of drugs and poisoning cases.

Methods

A 6 months study was conducted. The clinical pharmacist used to take part in the ward rounds with the physician for actively monitoring of any ADRs. The data was collected from the identified patient’s case sheets. The prescriptions given to the patient was noted on the data collection form.

RESULT

Details of Gender of the Patient

During the study period a total of 61 patients were analysed, out of which 49.18% were male and 50.82% were females.

Table 1: Distribution of patients according to Gender.

Gender	No: of cases	Percentage
Male	30	49.18%
Female	31	50.82%
Total	61	100%

Distribution of Patients with Respect to Age

Out of 61 patients studied the majority of the patients belonged to the age group of 19-64 years (56.67%), followed by 65-80 years (23.33%) and 0-18 years (20%) of age groups. The youngest patient was two and half month old and the oldest was 79 years old.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients with respect to Age.

Age group	No: of cases (n)	Percentage
Pediatrics (≤ 18)	11	20%
Adults (19-64)	33	56.67%
Geriatrics (≥ 65)	17	23.33%
TOTAL	61	100%

Distribution of Cases with Respect to Drug Eruptions

Among the various known patterns of ADRs, the most commonly reported ADRs were rashes (27.87%), followed by pruritis (6.55%), urticaria (4.92%), SJS (4.92%), etc.

Table 3: Types of Drug Eruptions.

Types of drug eruptions	No: of cases	Percentage
Rash	17	27.87%
Pruritis	4	6.55%
Vomiting	4	6.55%
Urticaria	3	4.92%
Steven Johnson Syndrome	3	4.92%
Hyper pigmentation	2	3.28%
Hypersensitivity	2	3.28%
Hypoglycemia	2	3.28%
Skin atrophy	2	3.28%
Nephrotoxicity	2	3.28%
Angioedema	2	3.28%
Dyskinesia	1	1.64%
Gastritis	1	1.64%
Psoriasis	1	1.64%
Hyponatremia	1	1.64%
Haematoma	1	1.64%
Chest pain & Breathlessness	1	1.64%
Hepatotoxicity	1	1.64%
Galactorrhea	1	1.64%
Others	10	16.39%
Total	61	100%

Distribution of Organ System Affected by ADRs

A total of 29 different types of ADRs were reported from 10 different organ systems. The commonly affected organ system were skin 39(63.93%) followed by gastrointestinal system 11(18.03%) and endocrine & metabolic system 3(4.92%). The commonly reported ADRs under each organ systems were rash (27.87%), vomiting (6.55%) and hypoglycemia (3.28%) respectively.

Table 4: Organ System affected by ADRs.

Organ System	No: of cases (n)	Percentage
Skin	39	63.93%
Gastrointestinal	11	18.03%
Endocrine & Metabolic	3	4.92%
Renal	2	3.28%
Respiratory	1	1.64%
Hepatic	1	1.64%
Hematologic	1	1.64%
Musculoskeletal	1	1.64%
Psychiatric	1	1.64%
Reproductive	1	1.64%
Total	61	100%

Distribution of ADRs based on drug class

From the total of 61 ADRs reported, 26 (42.62%) ADRs were associated with antibiotics followed by anti-ulceratives 4(6.56%) and the least were associated with alpha blocker (1.64%), anti-parkinson (1.64%), oral hypoglycemic (1.64%), etc.

Table 5: Distribution of ADRs Based on Drug Class.

Drug Class	No: Of ADRs	Percentage
Antibiotics	26	42.62%
Anti-ulcerative	4	6.56%
Hormone	3	4.92%
Antipsycotics	3	4.92%
Antihypertensives	2	3.28%
Antidepressants	2	3.28%
Anticonvulsants	2	3.28%
Corticosteroids	2	3.28%
Vaccine	2	3.28%
Antimetabolite	2	3.28%
NSAIDs	2	3.28%
Iron supplements	1	1.64%
Alpha blockers	1	1.64%
Antiparkinson	1	1.64%
Multivitamin	1	1.64%
Oral Hypoglycemia	1	1.64%
Mucolytics	1	1.64%
Anticoagulants	1	1.64%
Antifungal	1	1.64%
Antituberculosis	1	1.64%
Vitamin B Complex	1	1.64%
Emollients	1	1.64%
Total	61	100.00%

Commonly incriminated drugs in drug eruption

In a total of 61 cases, majority of the ADRs were caused by antibiotics. Of which Ceftriaxone (8.2%) was the most offending drug followed by Cefixime (4.9%), Piperacillin+Tazobactam (4.9%), Amoxicillin (3.28%), etc. The least incriminated drugs were Omeprazole, Ciprofloxacin, Aspirin, Levodopa and Phenytoin and these were 1.64% each.

Distribution of ADRs based on wards

A total of 61 ADRs were reported among which 43 ADRs were from in-patient department in that 22 ADRs (36.06%) were reported from medical ward followed by 6 ADRs (9.84%) from the pediatric ward. 18 ADRs were reported from out-patient department in that 8 ADRs were reported from dermatology ward (13.11%) followed by casualty in which 3 (4.92%) ADRs were reported. The least were reported from gynecology (1.64%), neurology (1.64%) and orthopedics (1.64%).

Table 7: Distribution of ADRs based on wards.

Departments	Wards	No: of ADRs n(%)	Total
Inpatient Department	Medical ward	22(36.06%)	43 (70.49%)
	Pediatric ward	6(9.84%)	
	Dermatology ward	4(6.55%)	
	Psychiatry ward	3(4.92%)	
	ICU	3(4.92%)	
	Surgery ward	2(3.28%)	
	Urology	1(1.64%)	
	Emergency	1(1.64%)	
	Orthopedics	1(1.64%)	
Outpatient Department	Dermatology	8(13.11%)	18 (29.51%)
	Casualty	3(4.92%)	
	Pediatric	2(3.28%)	
	Medicine	2(3.28%)	
	Neurology	1(1.64%)	
	Gynecology	1(1.64%)	
	Orthopedics	1(1.64%)	
	Total		61

Causality Assessment**WHO-UMC scale**

In the WHO-UMC scale most of the ADRs reported were probable (39.34%), followed by possible (36.07%).

Table 8: Causality assessment using WHO-UMC scale.

WHO-UMC causality criteria	No: of ADRs (n)	Percentage
Certain	11	18.03%
Probable	24	39.34%
Possible	22	36.07%
Unlikely	0	0%
Conditional/Unclassified	3	4.92%
Unassessable /Unclassifiable	1	1.64%
Total	61	100%

[Adapted from WHO-UMC scale]

Naranjo's Causality Assessment

According to Naranjo's scale majority of the ADRs were probable 41 (67.21%) followed by possible 15 (24.59%) and definite 5 (8.2%).

Table 9: Naranjo's Causality Assessment.

Naranjo's Algorithm	No: of ADRs (n)	Percentage
Definite	5	8.2%
Probable	41	67.21%
Possible	15	24.59%
Unlikely	0	0%
Total	61	100%

[Adapted from Naranjo's causality assessment]

Seriousness of the Adverse Drug Reaction

27.86% of ADRs requires inpatient hospitalization and 26.23% requires intervention to prevent permanent impairment or damage. Of the total 61 cases, 15 were life threatening (24.6%) and 1 resulted in significant disability (1.64%).

Table 10: Seriousness of Adverse Drug Reaction.

SERIOUS			
SL. NO	Seriousness of ADRs	Number of ADRs	Percentage
1	Requires inpatient hospitalization	17	27.86%
2	Require intervention to prevent permanent impairment or damage	16	26.23 %
3	Life threatening	15	24.6%
4	Results in persistent/significant disability	1	1.64%
	NON- SERIOUS	8	19.67%
	TOTAL	61	100 %

Out of the 61 cases, 80.33% of Adverse Drug Reactions were serious and only 19.67% were non-serious.

Table 11: Distribution of ADRs Based On Seriousness.

Seriousness	No: of ADRs	Percentage
Serious	49	80.33%
Non-Serious	12	19.67%
Total	61	100 %

Severity Assessment based on Hartwig and Siegel's scale

Of the total of 61 cases 44 were moderately severe (72.13%) followed by 9 (14.76%) ADRs of mild severity and 8(13.11%) ADRs of severe severity.

Table 12 Severity Assessment Based on Hartwig and Siegel's Scale.

Severity	No of ADRs (n)	Percentage	Total
Mild			
Level 1	5	8.2%	14.76%
Level 2	4	6.56%	
Moderate			
Level 3	21	34.43%	72.13%
Level 4a	9	14.75%	
Level 4b	14	22.95%	
Severe			
Level 5	8	13.11%	13.11%
Level 6	0	0	
Level 7	0	0	
Total	61		100%

[Adapted from Hartwig and Siegel's scale]

Predictability of Reported ADRs

In our study, the results showed that 56 (91.80%) ADRs were predictable and 5(8.2%) were non-predictable.

Table 13: Predictability of Reported ADRs.

Predictability	No: of cases (n)	Percentage
Predictable	56	91.80%
Non predictable	5	8.2 %
Total	61	100%

Preventability Assessment Based on Schumock and Thornton's criteria

In our study the result showed that 42 ADRs were probably preventable (75.41%) followed by definitely preventable 20 (16.39%) and 5 ADRs were (8.2%) not preventable.

Table 14: Preventability Assessment.

Preventability	No: of cases	Percentage (%)
Definitely preventable	10	16.39
Probably preventable	46	75.41
Not preventable	5	8.2
Total	61	100

Outcome of management of ADRs

The suspected drug was withdrawn (68.85%) in most of the ADRs. In 14 cases dose was altered (22.95) and 43 requires symptomatic treatment (70.49%), 12 requires specific treatment (19.67%).

Table 15: Outcome of Management of ADRs.

Management of ADR	No: of ADRs	
Fate of the suspected drug	Drug withdrawn	42 (68.85%)
	No change	5 (8.2%)
	Dose altered	14 (22.95%)
Treatment given	Specific	12 (19.67%)
	Symptomatic	43 (70.49%)
	No treatment	6 (9.84%)

Outcome of ADRs

Most of the ADRs were recovered 30 (49.18%), which is followed by 22 (36.07%) of recovering ADRs.

Table 16: Shows outcome of ADRs.

Outcome of ADR	Number of ADR (n)
Fatal	0
Recovered	30 (49.18%)
Continuing	1 (1.64%)
Recovering	22 (36.07%)
Unknown	8 (13.11%)
Total	61 (100%)

DISCUSSION

The site at which the study was conducted had one of the ADR Monitoring Centre (AMC) at SSIMS & RC, Davangere and hence the suspected ADRs were also notified into National Pharmacovigilance Program of India. During the period of 6 months a total of 61 cases were reported with ADRs. However some researchers have found that the incidence of ADRs were unrelated to gender[9], which supports our findings that there was not much significant difference between men and women on the rate of ADRs (female: 50.82%, male: 49.18%).

Our study showed that the adult group (>19) had significantly higher rate (56.67%) of ADRs reported than those of the pediatric group (20%) and the geriatric group (23.33%) which was same as the study conducted by Lobo et al[9]. The reason why higher incidence is observed in adults could be that they have more accessibility to medical health care and awareness to come back to the treating physician to report ADR[3].

In the current study, the reports received from out-patient department were lower than ADRs among inpatient departments. Inpatient department based reports comprised of 70.49% and ADR reported from outpatient department were 29.51% similar to the results observed from the study of Palanisamy S et al[10] Department of medicine (39.34%) reported most of the ADRs. In this study the dermatology department (19.66%) became the second major department to report ADR. However, a few departments like ophthalmology and ENT did not contribute any ADR. The lower reporting from OPD patients can be overcome by encouraging and educating patients to report.

In our study the organ system that was affected with highest frequency of adverse reactions was the skin (63.93%) which was similar to the study conducted by Agrawal M et al[3]. The most suspected ADR were rashes i.e, in 17 (27.87%) cases which was similar to the results obtained from the studies conducted by Harsha Ramakrishnaiah et al[11].

The most common offending drug classes were antibiotics 26 (42.62%). The studies of Ashok Kumar D et al[12], Harsha Ramakrishnaiah et al[11] and R Priyadarshini et al[13] also showed that the most common offending drug classes were antibiotics. Ceftriaxone (8.2%) was highly suspected drug which was similar to the results from the study of Harsha Ramakrishnaiah et al[11]. The causality assessment done by using WHO scale reveals that 39.34% of ADRs were probably drug related as similar to the results in the study by Arvind Kumar Sharma et al[2]. In the assessment done by Naranjo's scale, among the 61 reported ADRs, 8.2% of ADRs were definite, 67.21% of ADRs were probable and 24.59% of ADRs were possible, which are similar to the results in the studies of R Arulmani et al[6]. De-challenge and re-challenge were done after identification of ADRs.

In the present study, based on the evaluation of severity using Hartwig and Siegel scale 8 ADRs were of highly severe and the rest 44 ADRs were of moderately severe and 9 were of mild severity and was similar to the findings reported in the study done by Harsha Ramakrishnaiah et al[11].

Result of present study showed most of ADRs was probably preventable (75.41%) as similar to the results of the study conducted by Harsha Ramakrishnaiah et al[11]. On evaluation all the ADRs may have been preventable, if proper precaution were taken by the patients like, they should carry a drug list indicating which drugs they are allergic to at the time of hospital visit to avoid reactions again, thus can save health system resources and reduce harm to the patient. In our study the reactions that were non-predictable was 8.2% and predictable was 91.8% which is similar to the results of Ashok Kumar D et al[12].

In this study, most of the offending medications were discontinued (68.85%) and symptomatic treatments (70.49%) were given which was similar to the study of Lobo et al[9]. The clinical treatments were implemented to relieve symptoms, whereas no treatment (9.84%) was administered in some cases due to the presence of only a mild ADR. None of the drugs causing ADR led to mortality among the recorded cases.

For patients who do not come back for follow up, some steps should be taken to consider them and give more attention for better patient care. Patient awareness regarding OTC drugs and self-medications should also be strengthened. When an adverse drug reaction has been diagnosed and treated, clear information must be provided to the patient regarding his/her drug reaction. Advise patients to carry a card containing the name of the medications that they are allergic to.

There is a need to facilitate ADR follow-ups by health professionals by the pharmacovigilance system as they are directly involved in patient care. Finally, adverse drug reactions should be reported to the manufacturer and the regulatory agency especially if the reaction is rare, serious or unexpected.

CONCLUSION

Adverse drug reactions are an unavoidable risk factor associated with the use of modern medicines. However, careful attention to dosage, age, and renal function can minimize the risk of developing ADRs in many patients. From our study we concluded that ADRs is a common occurrence and awareness to the health care professionals should be essential for diagnosis and prevention.

ABBREVIATIONS

SSIMS & RC	– Shamanur Shivashankarappa Institute of Medical Science & Research Centre
ADR(s)	– Adverse Drug Reaction(s)
WHO	– World Health Organisation
UMC	– Uppsala Monitoring Centre
ICSR	– Individual Case Safety Report
CDSCO	– Central Drugs Standard control Organization
NCC	– National Coordination Centre
PvPI	– Pharmacovigilance Programme of India
SJS	– Steven Johnson Syndrome
NSAIDs	– Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs
ICU	– Intensive Care Unit
AMC	– Adverse Reaction Monitoring Centre
OTC	– Over the Counter
OPD	– Out Patient Department

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